

Job Rotation for Optimal Performance of Employees in the Organizations

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ABSTRACT

Job rotation is a human resource practice by which where an employee is rotated on different job functions in the organization enhance his practical knowledge, skills and expertise in his professional job. Job rotation is a process through a employee rotated at the various positions in the organization to enhance the functional expertise of the employees in all areas of the organization.

The research study is focused on to analyze the effect of Job Rotation on employees' performance in private organizations. The survey technique is used for the collection of data gathered from 100 employees including males and females working in 5 private organizations in Pakistan. Hence, SPSS is used to analyze the effect of job rotation on performance of employees at all levels of Management and data is analyzed by using Descriptive analysis. The research finding has mentioned that job rotation does effect on the performance of employees in the organizations. Job rotation positively influences on employees' performance by improving their skills, expertise in the various functional areas of the management of the organization and develop enough diversity in the career development of the employee.

Keywords: Job rotation, job skills, job expertise, employees performance, career development

1. Introduction:

The job rotation is a process through which employee is transferred from one position to another position in various functional areas of the organization. Senge (1999) in his research work has applied systematic movement of employees from one job to another. The

job rotation provides the opportunity to the employee who is rotated without changing the portfolio and accumulates experience in various functional areas of the organization (Champion et al., 1994).

The job rotation is known as method of job design which provides opportunity to the employees to learn job skills at the various departments of the organization and remove the fatigue of employees working at the same position all the time by changing their assignment after certain period of time. The challenges of working at the new assignment develop a spirit of improving morale in the working environment. For the implementation of job rotation process in the organization, the management should focus on the quality of work experience of the employees rather than quantity of the work (Jorgensen, 2005). In order to cope with new challenges and developments in the business environment, it has become vital for the organizations to develop and improve required skills of the employees.

The current organizations are focusing on equipping employees with the knowledge and capabilities to enhance the performance of organization (Ortega, 2001). In this context, the job rotation is considered a vital component of work layout in the organization. Through job rotation, the employee is rotated at different positions to obtain competency in various functional areas of the organization (Gomez & Lorente, 2004). For instance, the Federal Government Learning and development policy of United Arab Emirates had stopped the culture of staying employees on the same position for a long

period of time and allows the qualified employees to be rotated at the leading positions at the various functional areas of the organization. Job rotation process can be applied to all employees at the different levels of management in the organization. It has different impact on the performance of employees and known as one of the effective way of developing abilities and deep understanding of the employees in the various functional areas of the organization (Erickson & Ortega, 2006).

Job rotation is considered viable method for the career development of the organization who intend to seek generalist rather than technical career path and want to obtain rapid exposure to wide range of jobs within the organization. Besides that it provides flexible working environment to multi-tasking working capabilities. Due to these optimistic effects, the organizations are increasingly adopting the process of job rotation (Mohsan et al., 2012). It is argued that job rotation releases the job stress of the employees and it enhances the occupational status of the employees. Further, it promotes psychological and physical health, develop a positive attitude, and provide the new perspective of learning at various jobs and increases self-motivation towards their position in the organization(James, 2000).

The research study conducted by Ortega and Weichel has observed that job rotation can be used by the organizations for the development of knowledge and fusion of the employees in breadth and depth. The job rotation strategy can only effect those employees who are rotated at the different positions to gain mastery on new knowledge and integrate all facets of knowledge resources in the organization. Job rotation is mainly consisting of three elements; Individual learning, knowledge from outside source and reciprocal interaction between the employees. But,

there are still issues and problems persisted in the job rotation process. (Jorgenson, 2005).

This research study is focused on to evaluate the effects of job rotation on the performance of employees in the organization. The study has targeted only those organizations where the job rotation process is adopted with the purpose of enhancing performance of the employees.

2. Research Methodology:

This research is based on quantitative study and close ended survey method was used to gather data. The study has targeted 100 employees of 5 different private organizations (i.e banks and communication)working at different levels of management for the collection of data. The data is gathering through using questionnaire instrument and it is based on 5 likert scale (strongly agree to strongly disagree).The descriptive analysis technique is used to analyze the gathered data from the organizations.

3. Job Rotation for optimal performance.

Job rotation is used by the organization to enhance job skills and knowledge of employees by rotating them at various jobs and relieve boredom of staying at same position all the time. It increases the skill variation and employees performance in the organization.

3.1. Job Rotation and Employees Performance

Job rotation process is an effective operational system to improve human capital performance and productivity in organizations. Moving from one position to another for set period of time, result in learning new skills and experiences which brings the diversity in the functional capability of the employees in the organization.

Figure: 1

Developing skills and expertise of employees is a prerequisite for organizational dynamics and productivity. Job rotation is used by organizations to develop organizational capabilities. In human

resources management, talent is defined as an individual's unique capital that makes employees more competitive in private organization. The job rotation system improves intellectual capital and innovation and job skills of employees.

H1: Job rotation develops employee's skills and expertise in various functional areas of the organization

3.2 Job Rotation enhances employee's efficiency in the organization

Job satisfaction is a most important element in management and organization area. Job satisfaction is known as a part of organizational commitments. Job rotation is a way to achieve human resource efficiency and job satisfaction of employees. Job rotation reduces boredom level of employees and keeps them motivated about their current job. Job rotation enriches employees with knowledge and expertise in required functional areas of the organization.

H2: Job Rotation enhances capability of the employee's job performance

3.3. Job rotation brings the diversity in career development of the employees

Job rotation does not only provides the opportunity to the employees to enhance their jobs skill and knowledge but also provides the chance to learn diverse job functions in the organization. The challenge of perform at a different position make them to learn diverse expertise and also open to workers to new possibilities with their careers.

H3: Job rotation increases functional diversity in career development of employees in the organization. Job rotation is an approach which shows the employees perceptions and attitudes towards their work and their role in organization. It shows employees confidence, make them more competitive and self-determinative.

Conceptual framework of optimal performance

Figure: 2

The above frame work is developed on the basis of research hypothesis. The frame is depicting the picture of job rotation's effects on the performance of the employees in the organization. The frame work mentioned that the job rotation enhance the skills and expertise, capability of job performance and functional diversity in the career development of the employees in the organization.

4. Research Findings

Descriptive analysis is performed to analyze effect of job rotation in enhancing the performance of employee's in organizations of Pakistan. Job rotation is a very effective practice to develop employee's job

skills, job diversity and confidence. The highest mean scores attained were associated with job rotation as a tool for employee's psychological empowerment (mean= 2.16), enough diversity within a career path of employees (mean=2.12), job satisfaction increases (mean=2.08).With respect to the mean response scores, the results show that the respondents appeared to agree to increase skills (mean=1.68,SD=0.513) and job expertise (mean=2.08, SD= 0.786), it has provided enough diversity in the career path of the employees(mean=2.12, SD= 1.081).

H1: Job rotation develops employee's skills and expertise in various functional areas of the organization

Graph#1

Showing the research finding in above graph-1 that Job rotation helps employees to develop more skills and expertise that have positive effect on their job performance. (Mean=1.68, SD=0.51). The analysis has provided significant mean value which shows that job rotation has developed skills and expertise of the employees in the organization. Hence on the basis of above result shown in the Graph-1, the H1 hypothesis

proved to be right that job rotation develops expertise and skill of the employees.

H2: Job Rotation enhances efficiency of the employees in performing their jobs.

Graph#2 (SD=0.90 Mean=1.92)

The research finding in the above graph-2, shows that job rotation enhance efficiency of the employees in performing their jobs. In sum up (30%+50%) = 85% employs agrees that job rotation enhances their job efficiency in the organization. Hence, on the basis of above result mentioned in the graph-II and significant

mean value, it is proved that the job rotation enhances the efficiency of employees in the organization.

H3: Job rotation increases functional diversity in career development of employees in the organization.

Graph# 3

In the above graph# 3 below, we can see job rotation provides enough diversity in the career development of employees with the (Mean=2.06, SD=1.00). The result has provided significant Mean value and it can be concluded that job rotation increases the functional diversity of the employees in their career development. The above graph shows that 30% strongly agree and 50% agree that through job rotation they gained enough diversity in the career development.

Conclusion

It is concluded that job rotation practice is one of the best approach that helps organizations to hunt a best human resource talent with the organization and it also provides opportunity to the employees to explore his own potential and enhance expertise in various functional areas of the organization. The research was conducted on the analyzing the effects of job rotation in enhancing the job performance. The study has developed three hypothesis and analysis was conducted on the basis of three hypothesis. The research findings in the study have showed that job rotation as a strategy had a significantly enhances the performance of the employees in the organization.

The research findings shown in the graphs has mentioned that job rotation develops employee's skills and expertise in all functional areas of the organization, job Rotation enhances efficiency of the employees in performing their jobs and it also increases functional diversity in career development of employees in the organization. On the basis of research findings, it is concluded that that job rotation

enhances the performance of employees in the organizations. These results also suggest that job rotation in organizations should know how employees enhances their performance and diversity within career path, job satisfaction expertise, skills and gain confidence.

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